

BLACK OCEAN STRATEGY - A PROBE INTO A NEW TYPE OF STRATEGY USED FOR ORGANIZATIONAL SUCCESS

Dr. P. S. Aithal & Dr. P. M. Suresh Kumar

Srinivas Institute of Management Studies, Pandeshwar, Mangalore - 575 001, INDIA

ABSTRACT

Strategic planning and decision making has an important role in organizational development and sustainability. Various types of strategies are used in strategic management such as Red ocean strategy, Blue ocean strategy, Green ocean strategy and Purple ocean strategy. These strategies are used in organizations by top level executive managers for long term organizational sustainability and to face or deviate from the competition. Based on organizational analysis, it is observed that some of the organizations especially in developing countries use a new type of strategy for sustainability at least for short term to overcome their high intensity problems and to get quick relief from the problems. In this paper we have generalized such a strategy and named it as "Black Ocean Strategy". Based on observation and focus group study we developed this concept and studied the conditions, characteristics and procedure of this model of decision making. We have studied the reasons why certain firms opt for Black ocean strategy while making decisions for sustainability and consequences of such strategic decisions through investment/perceived Risk Matrix. We have also compared the different strategic choices with that of Black ocean strategy. The details and consequences of such strategy followed in some organizations are also discussed.

KEYWORDS : Strategy types, Red ocean strategy, Blue ocean strategy, Black ocean strategy, Comparison of different strategies. Characteristics of Black ocean strategy.

1. INTRODUCTION

A strategy is a long-term plan for the whole organisation or for an individual. Corporate strategy may be defined as "The positioning and relating of the firm/organisation to its environment in a way which will assure its continued success and make it sure from surprises" [1]. A variety of factors drive organizations to adopt strategies in order to emerge successful such for instance is growth, stability, profitability and efficiency. Growth involves the expansion of a business, its markets, products, size etc. Successful growth strategies are based on having the resources to support growth, identifying the markets that make growth worthwhile being better in competition in these growth markets. Stability involves a consolidation strategy for the organisation, often before a period of growth. The organisation needs to establish clear procedures and systems during this period before moving on. Seeking profit is an important business strategy, particularly in organisations where shareholders have considerable influence. Efficiency is concerned with how well resources have been used in meeting organisational objectives. It is important for public sector service organisations to show that taxpayers funds have been used well. This apart, market leadership strategies aims to be number one in market. The market leader is able to gain considerable cost advantages over rivals because by definition other firms will have a smaller market share and therefore fewer opportunities for economies of scale. Beyond all these survival is essential in a highly competitive business environment. Survival is the key to most organisations. Only by surviving they are able to develop other strategies. Apart from above, strategies of an organization or individual are divided into another class as (1) competitive strategies also called Red ocean strategies [2], (2) monopoly strategy called Blue ocean strategy [3], (3) sustainable strategy called Green ocean strategy [4], and (4) a mix of Blue and Green called Purple ocean strategy [5].

Think of the market as an ocean and the competing organizations as sharks fighting each other and striving to prevail. The bloodshed makes the ocean turn red. That is why the competing strategies followed by the organizations are called red ocean strategies [6]. Red oceans represent all the industries in existence today in the known market space. In red oceans, industry boundaries are defined and accepted, and the competitive rules of the game are well understood. Here, companies try to outperform their rivals in order to grab a greater share of existing demand. As the space gets more and more crowded, prospects for profits and growth are reduced. Products turn into commodities, and increasing competition turns the water bloody. Red ocean strategy supports to compete in existing market space, beat the competition, exploit existing demand, make the value/cost trade-off, align the whole system of a company's activities with its strategic choice of differentiation or low cost [6].

Blue oceans denote all the industries not in existence today- the unknown market space, untainted by competition. In blue oceans, demand is created rather than fought over. There is ample opportunity for growth that is both profitable and rapid. There are two ways to create blue oceans. In a few cases, companies can give rise to completely new industries, as eBay did with the online auction industry. But in most cases, a blue ocean is created from within a red ocean when a company alters the boundaries of an existing industry. Blue ocean strategy supports to create uncontested market space, make the competition irrelevant, create and capture new demand, break the value/cost trade-off, align the whole system of a company's activities in pursuit of differentiation and low cost [7].

Green Ocean Strategy is a recent strategic outcome with two different types of schools of thought. According to first school of thought, it is a strategy to gauge the impact of environmental footprint on human lives. From different unstructured documents like newspapers, magazines, world wide web pages, it is revealed that automobile industry happens to be one of the largest contributors of environmental pollution throughout the world. India, as an emerging economy, has become a lucrative market destination for automobiles. Due to high level of global competition, a plethora of global automobile players have crowded in this second largest market. This phenomenon coupled with influx of other industries has blown up the environmental footprint in India leaving an adverse impact on human lives [8]. According to second school of thought, it is a hybrid mechanism which combines the best things that characterize Blue ocean and Red ocean strategies. The keyword in discussing this theory is *sustainability* and there can be no one-size-fits-all formula governing the innovation mechanism of an organization [9 - 10].

Based on organizational analysis, it is observed that some of the organizations and individuals especially in developing countries use a new type of strategy for survival and sustainability at least for short term to overcome their intensive problem and to get quick relief from the problems. In this paper we have generalized such a strategy and named it as "Black Ocean Strategy". Black ocean strategy is a kind of survival strategy to foresee the organizational problems and solve them successfully to continue in its business market by means of a kind of black magic may be legally or illegally, ethically or unethically. Based on our observation and focus group study we have developed this concept systematically and studied the conditions and characteristics of this model of decision-making called Black ocean strategy. We have studied the reasons why certain firms and certain individuals at its helm follow Black ocean strategy while making decision for survival and consequences of such strategic decisions through investment/perceived Risk Matrix. We have also compared red ocean strategy & Black ocean strategy, blue ocean strategy

& Black ocean strategy, and green ocean strategy and Black ocean strategy used in organizations. Finally the details and consequences of Black ocean strategy followed by few organizations are discussed.

2. STRATEGIES RE-VISITED

A discussion on prevailing strategies for managerial decision making based on the available literature is attempted here. Red oceans represent the traditional existing industries and known market space, where industry boundaries are defined and accepted, competitive rules of the game are known, outperform the rivals to grab a greater share of existing demand at a crowded market space. The prospects for profits and growth are limited [6]. Red ocean strategy refers to a saturated market in which there is fierce competition because it is already crowded with companies providing the same type of products and services, leading to price wars which are detrimental to innovation [11]. For example, recently Apple launched the latest version of its smartphone for end users, iPhone 5, at a time when the market is already saturated with Blackberry, Nokia, Samsung and other Android phone segments, a clear example of a red ocean strategy [9]. Red Ocean Strategy consists of either cost leadership or product/service differentiation strategy. In cost leadership strategy, the company aims on being the lower cost product or service supplier in the industry. There can be only one low cost leader company in a specific market. It should have high initial investment being able to create economy of scale in the production. Its main cause should be to reduce cost in any means such as cost reduction in R & D, service, sales force, advertising so its products will be offered in lowest price without compromise quality with those of competitors. In differentiation strategy, the company aims to develop a product or service that creates its consumer perception of being unique. Customer should believe that this product or service is different or superior than its competitive products/service in the industry/ market and if succeed in that the company differentiates from the competition [6]. Porter suggested that a company should focus in one strategy and not try to combine them. He claims that a company that follows more than one competitive strategy is facing the danger to be stacked in the middle of the competitive market place, without having a competitive advantage and be doomed to be underachieve or even worst eventually die [6]. In red ocean strategy the market segment borders are limited and the competition rules are known to every competitors. As the competitors multiply, the expected income, profit, and growth of the company decreases. Companies on red ocean witness low income due to their commodity products and lack of loyal customers. These factors force the companies to increase their efficiency by decreasing their functional costs and by increasing their marketing expenses. These techniques of renewing of value are not very effective for companies because usually its competitors will imitate its strategy [3].

The blue oceans stand for completely new and undiscovered markets and opportunities with new value creations, new customer bases and no competition. Demand is created, growth is profitable and rapid, competition is irrelevant, rules of the game are not set. Wide and deep potential of market space that is not yet explored is the “blue ocean”. It is deep and powerful in terms of profitable growth, and infinite [9]. Basically, the Blue ocean strategy indicates a radical or disruptive innovation where companies innovate so that they do not have to compete with products from other companies, but create separate categories of products in their own right, thus, setting the benchmark as an early mover in the given segment [11 - 13]. This means the blue oceans are untapped and uncontested markets that provide little or no competition for the business. For instance, when Apple had launched iPhone in 2008, it was a pioneer in the smartphone segment, thus, their innovation succeeded in terms of the Blue ocean strategy [7]. Kim and Mauborgne [7] made detailed study from 2004 where they analysed 150 companies within 30 industries over 100 years and found that two kinds of markets called the “blue and red oceans”, existed in their opinion. But only the companies from the blue ocean markets were able to achieve true success. As per the results of Kim & Mauborgne [7], only 14% of all studied business launches were made within the Blue Ocean markets, but these 14% achieved 38% revenue impact and about 62% of profit impact. Compared to the majority of 86% business launches in red oceans, which were able to get 39% of the total profit impact. The basic ideas used for the Blue Ocean Strategy can be summarized as 1) ignoring competition, 2) creation of new markets, 3) focus on new customers and 4) value innovation.

Other researchers offer solutions in their paper how organizations could create new market space, some use also integrated theoretical frameworks [14] remotely comparable to the Blue Ocean Strategy that offers also frameworks and tools for creating uncontested market space. Berry et al. [15] investigated in their paper "Creating New Markets Through Service Innovation" the different types of the market creating service innovations, describing niche factors they discovered to enable new innovations for market creation. Anderson and Gatington [16] showed in their research “Firms and the creation of new markets” that new markets can be generated by certain actions of firms. According to them, a market is being created when economic actors shift resources to that firm's solution to satisfy the latent customer need. Spencer et al. [17] researched in their paper “How Governments Matter to New Industry Creation” the influence of governments on new industry creation. According to them, companies and institutions were influencing the governments' capabilities to support bricolage, or breakthrough approaches to technological entrepreneurship, which also lead to the creation of new industries. Some researchers mention that the Blue Ocean Strategy is most effective when markets are saturated or in decline. Therefore a

company should target completely new customer groups to increase their customer base [18]. Kim and Mauborgne [7] point out that companies not only have to outplay their competition, but furthermore completely ignore them by searching and entering new and uncontested markets.

The main key therefore is to find out 1) what customers seek when they buy a product or service and then 2) define a total solution. Besides that, the process of creating and discovering blue ocean markets is not about predicting and/or pre-allocating business trends. It is about leading managers who are able to reordering market realities in a fundamentally new way.

According to Burke et al., [19] the Blue Ocean Strategy is ascribed with lack in evidence, because only successful companies were studied and it depends on two basic but testable assumptions. First, the prediction that competition can be made irrelevant. Second, the trust that sufficient Blue Ocean markets are available to be chosen as a successful generic industry-wide strategy. Herman [20] argues that a successful implemented Blue Ocean Strategy will give a company only a limited, relatively peaceful, period of time. Herman [20] introduced the term of Unfair Advantage (UA) for the time period were a company is in a situation in which they become unique and adored by their customers, while competitors do not imitated them. This Unfair Advantage would go against the omnipresent business rules and giving the term a negative touch.

As per first school of thought, the green ocean strategy (GOS) refers to creating opportunities from environmental risks and pressures, environmental awareness among consumers, and environmental design, marketing and technologies. It is not just about companies carrying on with their business and taking care of the environment, it is more about companies taking care of the environment as their business and making profits along the way [21-24]. As per Starbucks company view, it is not serving coffee to customers, it is serving customers with coffee. Similarly, Sam Walton of Wal-Mart would say, profits are a by-product of good service. Some examples of GOS include General Electric's Ecomagination and Honda's Environmentology [25]. Green ocean strategy is the strategy of sustainable development under the guidance of harmonious belief; it refers to business operation theories, actions and procedures aiming at achieving sustainable development by increasing core and sustainable competence through actively undertaking corporate social responsibility and balanced management of stakeholders' interests, as well as maximizing economic and social values under the guidance of sustainable development theory. Sustainable development theory is the foundation of Green Ocean Strategy, and core competence is the source of sustainable competitive advantage; obtaining sustainable competitive advantage through systematic management of interests of stakeholders is the heart of Green Ocean Strategy [26]. Companies pursuing Green Ocean Strategy seek sustainable competitive advantage with both hard competence

and soft competence. Enterprises who participate in international competition need to establish a core competence. This includes “hard competence” and “soft competence”. Companies need both of these two kinds of competence to succeed in market competition, while soft competence plays a more important role to achieve a sustainable development [27]. Green Ocean Strategy admits that stakeholders have different views though they share some same stakes. From the perspectives of all parties, companies should make profits for a consecutive period of time (hopefully all the time); for employees, a company should maintain or enlarge the employment scale and provide satisfactory working environment; for suppliers, a company should make new orders continually; for the government, a company should pay taxes on time; for customers, a company should keep providing products that go with the quality and price demand of the market. Of all the factors above, the most basic one is to continually provide products that meet the demand and changes of the market [28]. According to Hou Shengtian & Chen Jiancheng [24], the research of the Green Ocean Strategy has entered the second stage. The first stage focused on normative research, aiming at clearing up some concepts, confirming the guiding research basis, theoretical foundation and researching methodology of green ocean strategy. The second stage of Green Ocean Strategy focus on the development of Harmony Monitor. Harmony Monitor is a management and evaluating tool to help an enterprise to fulfill its social obligation, to balance the relationship of stakeholders and to obtain sustainable competence.

According to the second school of thought, green ocean strategy is a hybrid mechanism which combines the best things that characterize blue ocean and red ocean strategies. The keyword is sustainability; in discussing this theory, the researcher asserts that there can be no one-size-fits-all formula governing the innovation mechanism of an organization [9]. The green ocean strategy will serve as a safety valve for companies trapped in the red ocean rut, facing intense competition, mounting price pressure, increasing bargaining power of customers, and flat demand despite overwhelming choice, essential characteristics of the blue ocean regime. In order to set a company on a strong, profitable, growth trajectory in the face of industry conditions using innovative revenue streams, yet ensuring it does not deviate from its core business objectives, the green ocean strategy will ensure a healthy balance for the company, preventing the huge risks that accrue due to going out all alone in an uncertain business environment. It is found that with the green ocean strategy, organizations neither have to hire additional workers, nor invest in more outsourcing projects than required. This would help retain employment of current workers, thus, managing good relations at the workplace while allowing the organization to pursue its innovation objectives in a sustainable, year-by-year pace [9- 10].

In a given business, reducing costs is not removing something completely from the system as proposed by Blue Ocean (removing the lions), but building on the commoditization and standardization of one layer, thereby bringing the costs down to close to zero. Building on the Red Ocean of community ownership a Blue Ocean of innovation and creativity, in a way that respects the value of the Red Ocean, is Purple Ocean Strategy [5].

3. BLACK OCEAN STRATEGY - CONCEPT DEVELOPMENT & DEFINITION

Based on organizational analysis, it is observed that some of the organizations especially in developing countries use a new type of strategy for sustainability at least for short term to overcome their high intensity problem and to get quick relief from it. Organizations who have objective of fast progression without much environmental bothering, ethical bothering and affected by sustainability dangers due to political, economic, social, or corruptive environmental reasons may choose some kind of strategy for quick relief. Organizations who face threat of starting business due to changes in socio-environmental conditions, adverse effect of laws of the land, trouble by pseudo-environmentalists, corrupted govt. officials & bureaucratic sanctions, unethical practice & tendency of stake-holders, and many other such reasons follow this type of strategy for their existence. This is also the case with organizations who have already set up the business and wants to grow inorganically by en-cashing all the opportunities and wants to over-take other existing competitors and to establish in market place quickly by either getting priority, or special consideration by using influence or by means of bribery, or using any other means to solve their problem of accumulating recourses, retaining labour, to have access to better technology, or to get special permissions to become monopoly in the business or to get official approval by law of land to fool/cheat stakeholders and the government in terms of profit sharing, availing tax-benefits etc. Such strategy gives short time relief to some organizations and long term support to other organizations and in both cases it will be life-saving strategy for those functioning in certain countries where business environment is not healthy. The strategy followed by such organizations "by taking risk by making their ethics at stake, for surviving in the business due to heavy pressure by the environment" can be termed as Black ocean strategy. It is a smart strategy to ensure win in market place and continuing business. It can be used internally in the organization to control and maintain industrial peace and to improve production efficiency or to improve service effectiveness or to solve internal problems or to maintain continued supply of raw materials or to decrease wastage. It can be external to the organization to maintain harmonious relationship with stake holders, government (both bureaucrats & politicians), publics or to expand market share through different collaborations, attractive advertisements etc. The strategy will ensure that the organization get rid of its problem either temporarily or permanently.

Black ocean strategy is an ancient strategy used in Indian philosophy as Atharva-veda. It is a type of black magic to ensure that an organization or an individual is reaching its or his goal irrespective of everything in reality goes against them. In such situation of anticipated failure in starting or continuing or competing in business, organizations should ensure that they are not announcing closure by accepting failure. Instead, they study the root cause of the problem, reasons of failure and taking decisions and actions to ensure win in the situation even if all environmental situations are against the organization. Black ocean strategy is not formulating strategy to face the competition by identifying various forces which affect the organizational business, it is not a method of developing monopoly product/service or identifying uncontested market space or a new way of serving the customer but it is a way of either killing the competitors, or creating a monopoly or solving life-threatening problems that arises due organization's own mistakes, or due to any environmental factors which makes the organization to shut down. Due to such un-expected problems which cannot be predicted in normal routine, many organizations follow this strategy in low ethical environment called Black ocean strategy. Such strategy gives temporary relief (oxygen) to the organization to continue its business and lift its head & get back its prestige in customers frame of reference and market place.

4. STRATEGIC DECISION MAKING MATRIX

No organization can stay and do the business ethically throughout its life-cycle even though it is decided to be so in its objectives and policies. This is due to environmental and social factors of the organization. Making decisions based on Red ocean competitive strategy or Blue ocean monopoly strategy is not adequate for organizations who have made heavy investments and face perceived risk based on internal and external uncertainties. A low invested organization can take a decision to shut down based on internal or environmental threat. A high invested organization cannot accept failure so easily and based on the nature of risk (low or high) can follow red ocean or Black ocean strategy to come out from the problem for sustainability (creating its own path by bending local situations to its favour). A low invested organization can adjust to the environment if the perceived risk is high by bending to the local situations & regulations (Green ocean strategy). The investment versus perceived risk matrix shown in Figure 1 explains why many organizations follow Black ocean strategy whenever essential in comparison to other strategies.

HIGH	Red Ocean Strategy	Black Ocean Strategy
LOW	Blue Ocean Strategy	Green Ocean Strategy
	LOW	HIGH

Fig. 1 : Investment versus perceived risk matrix.

5. CONDITIONS FOR BLACK OCEAN STRATEGY

What is Black ocean strategy and what is not ?

Any kind of non-ethical practices followed by organizations for their growth and survival in a given environmental situation is considered as Black ocean strategy. The Black ocean strategies followed by organizations will not be public and may not affect the name and fame (image) of the organizations. If known to everybody, the organization may get black-listed by government, stake holders like suppliers, investors, collaborators, sometimes by customers and even by publics. If the way of implementing Black ocean strategy involves huge corruption and injustice to the stake holders, such organizations may face problems for existence. Hence Black ocean strategy followed by organizations may be a back fire to the image of the organization and throw them into disaster if not used sparingly and carefully.

The necessary conditions for Black ocean strategy to be implemented in an organization are :

1. Challenge for survival.
2. Huge investment going to be waste.
3. Organization facing severe problem.
4. Existence of enormous and unusual opportunity

The sufficient conditions for Black ocean strategy (BOS) to be implemented in an organization are :

1. The internal structure and conditions of organization should support BOS
2. The environment should be such that there should be an opportunity to use BOS
3. BOS is the last option to solve the problem.
4. The organization is capable to digest the consequence of BOS

6. PROCEDURE OF ADOPTING BLACK OCEAN STRATEGY

The various steps to be followed by an organization while following Black ocean strategy for solving organizational challenges as a final solution for existence are shown in Figure 2.

Step 1 : Identify/sense the problem : Identify organizational problems which hinders the growth. This problem may be employee union problem, problems due to Govt. or regulatory body regulations or due to environmental regulations or quality regulations or Country tax payment regulations or marketing challenges of products/services.

Step 2 : Predict the solution : Assume the required solution to your organizational problem. This can be done by knowing what type of permission you need, or what type of solution in Labour union which benefit the organization, or what type of advertisement enhances your market share, or what are the ways to decrease/avoid taxes, or what type of category stakeholders bargaining power should be controlled, or how to get new technology at minimum cost etc.

Step 3 : Research different possibilities : Research for possible solutions through Black ocean strategy, which may include influence, lobbying, pressuring by identifying right person capable to do that and through legal or illegal manner. This strategy may include illegal and unethical ways of dealing involving corruption/bribery. This strategy is like winning the war without actually fighting it.

Step 4 : Choose Optimum Method : Identify optimum method of reaching the solution to solve above identified problems by using a suitable Black ocean strategy with minimal expenditure, minimal risk and minimum time, with assured result.

Step 5 : Maintain secrecy of success : Maintain secrecy of the procedure followed using BOS to avoid any risk of enquiry at any later stage and discard all evidence related to BOS and its implementation.

Fig. 2 : Block diagram of various steps involved in the procedure of adopting Black ocean strategy.

Step 6 : Do not repeat frequently : Once the serious problem of existence of organization is solved, do not follow BOS further with mere intension of making quick & huge profit unethically due to greediness. This may jeopardize the further function of the organization along with punishment to its directors.

7. CHARACTERISTICS OF BLACK OCEAN STRATEGY

Some of the prominent characteristics of Black ocean strategy are listed below :

1. Black ocean strategy is a short cut plan to win the game through alternative way by changing the rules of the game.
2. This strategy is used by organizations when they realize that the organization is failed to achieve its stated goal due to things going out of their control and affects heavily on its business.

3. Black ocean strategy contains set of practices which are considered as unethical in common business practice.
4. Black ocean strategy will not support to improve organizations efficiency or operational effectiveness.
5. It will help the organization to survive in disasters through different set of activities/practices which otherwise will not be used in regular practice in normal routine.
6. Black ocean strategy is not an alternative to red ocean, blue ocean and green ocean strategies but it is complementary to them as it supports the organization at times of disaster.
7. Black ocean strategy is a complement to other strategies such that it can provide winning edge in red ocean or provide support to make competition irrelevant in blue ocean by modifying internal policies and external regulations for individual organizations benefit.
8. Black ocean strategy is not used to position the company against competitive forces but it provides unique position against uncertainty due to un-accepted dangers due to organizational mistakes or due to un-supportive environmental situations.
9. Influence on Government or other statutory controlling/directing bodies to make the rule according to their requirement.
10. Generally suited to put influence or pressure on international permissions, collaborations and technology transfer.
11. Lobbying and influencing is also a form of Black ocean strategy to do organizations work and to retain or expand their market share.
12. Organizations are lobbying and influencing to save tax to be paid to the local government so that they can enhance profit and transfer such profits to other countries as investment to expand business.
13. Black ocean strategy aims to change the rules of the game according to organizational wish to en-cash better opportunities, or to solve serious problems, or to modify/create new policies & regulations.
14. This strategy is used only for temporary relax from the problems and should not be repeated due to greediness or continued benefit.
15. Black ocean strategy also include the strategy to kill the competitors by changing the rules of the game.

16. Black ocean strategy can also be used to create uncontested market/monopoly for at least short time by modifying the rules of the game.

17. Black ocean strategy can be used at corporate, business, and functional level depending upon the nature of problem to be solved at that level.

8. SOME BLACK OCEAN STRATEGIC FLOPS

Many companies and managers become famous and rich overnight, or sometimes fail and go to jail on the following day. This is due to improper handling of decisions and actions taken by strategy executor in the company. Those who maintain secrecy and have luck (various supportive environmental and internal factors at that time) turn out to be winners.

(1) Enron's India Strategy - In its Dabhol Power Project, Enron Multinational company used Black ocean strategy and admitted to a U.S. Congressional committee that it had spent US\$20 million to "educate Indians" on the benefits of its power project in Maharashtra. Un-official sources disclose that major part of this money is used to 'educate' Politicians and bureaucrats of State & Central Govt.

(2) Reliance Petro-chemicals Strategy : Un-official sources disclose that Reliance Petro-chemicals has taken paid services & consultancy of ONGC/other agencies of Govt. of India through its Black ocean strategy.

(3) MCI Strategy : As per certain undisclosed sources, Medical Council of India, a regulatory body of Medical education in India has developed stringent & unrealistic regulations to trouble the Medical education institutions which in-turn support the use of Black ocean strategy by institutions for survival.

(4) AICTE - India Strategy : Recently, All India Council for Technical Education has announced a regulation to all member colleges to compulsorily purchase large number of foreign online journals at huge cost every year, supplied by some specified foreign agencies. Such strategy supported the officials to deposit huge kick-back in foreign banks. Being intangible products, these journals had no much use for the colleges.

(5) Coca-Cola Gets Busted In Recent Illegal Guerrilla Advertisements : The advertisements released by some of the companies in their strategy to enhance market share, sends wrong message to the publics.

(6) Walmart's Black ocean strategy of bribery in India, Brazil, China, Mexico to get favour from local governments to expand its business and hence to enhance profit.

(7) In telecommunications, for instance, Indian companies acquired licenses at a knock-down price from the government with the aid of corrupt ministers using Black ocean strategy. They then sold stakes in the companies that held these licenses to foreign telecom majors seeking an entry into India. The foreign companies paid several times what the Indian entities had shelled out for the licenses. On paper, they look foolish, but not criminal. All the players would have been happy if the Supreme Court hadn't stepped in and cancelled the process.

(8) Agrigold, an Andhra Pradesh-based company is spreading its tentacles fast through its Black ocean strategy in Andhra Pradesh. Its owner is a former employee of now extinct Golden Forest Ltd, which vanished with several hundreds of crores of public money with the promise of easy and quick money and now facing criminal cases. It never returned the deposits it collected from public with the promise of high returns. Its representatives then claimed that it has huge tracts of land all over India and there is no threat to their deposits with the company. They never revealed that the company has no permission from the Reserve Bank of India to collect deposits from public.

(9) The top names in American business – from Apple to Xerox – have joined in the greatest tax dodge in world history. Using clever accounting games, these corporate have siphoned majestic sums out of the country and into tax-haven – where the money is untouchable by the IRS.

A global survey by Ernst & Young is equally blunt about the country: "Seventy percent of India respondents to our survey think that bribery and corruption are widespread in the country." According to the World Bank, India has a poor rating on business climate. "It is difficult for foreign companies to operate in India without being touched by the issue in some shape or form. The pervasive weakness in governance is bound to increase the risk faced by all companies, domestic and foreign, that they will also be impacted by corrupt practices through Black ocean strategy for sustainability."

9. REASONS FOR ADOPTING BLACK OCEAN STRATEGY

Using 'focus group study technique' developed by E. M. Rogers [29], we have identified various factors deciding Black ocean strategy of organizations. These factors are divided into internal, external and quasi-external based on their organizational structure and is given in Table 1.

Table 1 : Factors deciding Black ocean strategy of organizations.

S. No	External Factors	Quasi External Factors	Internal Factors
1	Trouble from Monitoring agencies	Ambition to overtake competitors	Continuous failure in business expansion
2	Illegal competition	Success of competitors who followed similar strategy	Internal pressure for sustainability & growth
3	Tough policies, rules and regulations of Govt. and possibility of breaking them	Quest to achieve monopoly & market expansion	Companies attitude of achieving quick profit
4	Corruption and bribery as shortcuts to success	Concern for relief from degradation of environment	Declined return on Heavy investment
5	Countries where ethical & social values are tumbling	To overcome labour might & militancy	Unethical managers with lack of values in the system
6	-	-	Hesitation to disclose mistakes
7	-	-	To maintain autocracy in leadership of the company

10. CONSEQUENCES OF BLACK OCEAN STRATEGY

Black ocean strategy may lead to success by solving serious or unexpected problems. Such problems include failure in business expansion, competition with other companies, blocks to growth, low return on investment, turn-around strategy on their advertisements, cut throat competition, greed for quick profit, overcoming regulations and possible breakdown, establish monopoly, keep clean image and public opinion, curb labour problems etc. As a managerial style this strategy enables maintaining control of leadership of the organization. Sometimes hesitation to admit mistakes will also lead to a situation to cover-up. Many Fortune 500 companies at one time or the other in their lifecycle have resorted to Black ocean strategy and obtained escape from failure. However, unless carefully handled it may lead to total failure due to exposure of illegality or unethical way of handling the troubles.

Classic examples of Black ocean strategy which ended up in scam are those of the following :

- (a) Sathyam Computers scam
- (b) 2G Spectrum scam
- (c) Sahara Group scam
- (d) Dabhol Power Project scam
- (e) Indian Coal gate Auction/Allocation scam
- (f) King Fisher Airlines failure and many more.

11. COMPARISON OF BLACK OCEAN STRATEGY WITH OTHER STRATEGIES

Based on the characteristics of Black ocean strategy, it can be compared with other prominent strategies. Table 2 contains comparison of major characteristics of Black ocean and Red ocean strategy. Similarly the comparison of Black ocean & Blue ocean strategy is given in Table 3 and the difference between Black ocean and Green ocean strategies is listed in Table 4.

Table 2 : Comparison of Black ocean & Red ocean strategy

S. No.	Red Ocean Strategy	Black Ocean Strategy
1	Position your company where the competitive forces are weakest.	Identify a location where the environmental instabilities are lowest.
2	Exploit changes in competitive forces	Exploit weakness of the controlling system/environment to overcome your organizations difficulty.
3	Reshape the forces in your favour	Control the problem and solve it in your favour
5	Industry structure drives competition and profitability, not whether an industry is emerging or mature, high tech or low tech, regulated or unregulated.	Ethical level of the Country drives the problems and solutions.
6	Provides competitive edge to the organization	Provides confidence for sustainability through exploiting the weakness of the external controlling systems.
7	Compete in existing market space	Solve the problems by en-cashing the

		weakness of the system
8	Beat the competition	Negate the competition
9	Make the value/cost trade-off	Break ethics/value trade-off
10	Align the whole system of a company's activities with its strategic choice of differentiation or low cost	Show your existence by tapping the weakness of the system

Table 3 : Comparison of Black ocean & Blue ocean strategy

S. No.	Blue Ocean Strategy	Black Ocean Strategy
1	Reconstruct/cross market boundaries	Conceive endless opportunity
2	Focus on big picture not numbers	Focus on critical problems
3	Reach beyond existing demand	Consolidate the existing & future demand
4	Get the strategic sequence right	Re-position the strategy
5	Create uncontested market space	Outright invasion
2	Makes the competition irrelevant	Undo competition
3	Create and capture new demand	Solve your problem by identifying weakness of the system and by en-cashing such opportunities
4	Break the value-cost trade-off	Break ethics/value trade-off
5	Align whole system of firm's activities in pursuit of differentiation and low cost.	Curb the pressure to change the system

Table 4 : Comparison of Black ocean & Green ocean strategy

S. No.	Green Ocean Strategy	Black Ocean Strategy
1	Decisions to improve the environment of a system	Decision to maintain existence of the system
2	Long term sustainability	Short term sustainability but essential for existence
3	Decreasing risk on functioning of the system	Solving the un-expected risk quickly

12. BLACK OCEAN STRATEGY AND INDIAN BUSINESS SCENARIO

One main accusation about large projects in India is acquisition of agricultural land and degradation of environment. In the cases of developed countries, usually the governmental bodies, media, and environmental groups are the ones who urge the companies to act responsibly whereby governments have taken all the possible measures to implement and enforce the laws to reduce or vanquish the possible threats to the environment which governments holds the power to punish violators of environment regulations and rewarding those companies who practices environmental friendly activities for example, Europe's government are rewarding those good companies who practices eco friendly with incentives like tax relief and others. Labour rights becomes a most common issue that always being focus on the existence of sweatshops or also known as sweat factory which is all about workers working in any type of very poor environment such as dangerous and unacceptable difficult work for very long hours with very low pay which violate the minimum wage law. Not only that, child labour laws may be violated as well and the work place might have highly hazardous situations including abuse of employee.

13. CONCLUSION

In this paper we have studied a frequently observed strategy followed by many organizations for solving their internal and external problems quietly by unannounced manner called Black ocean strategy. Many organizations in their life-cycle face such problems or opportunities to expand their business using such strategy especially in developing countries. It is also found that such strategy is used in many organizations even by taking decisions against their organizational ethics for survival. The country regulations framed by Govt. or the business/industry regulations framed by regulating agencies are so impracticable in such a way that the organizations are forced to plan and follow Black ocean strategy for survival. Based on our observation and focus group study we have developed this concept systematically and studied the conditions and characteristics of this model of decision making called Black ocean strategy. We have studied the reasons why certain firms follow Black ocean strategy while making decision for sustainability and consequences of such strategic decisions. We have also compared red ocean strategy & Black ocean strategy, blue ocean strategy & Black ocean strategy, and green ocean strategy and Black ocean strategy in organizations. Finally the details and consequences of Black ocean strategy followed by few organizations and individuals are discussed.

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